

Green RSE – Kirsty Pringle

- Build a community to work together to reduce the environmental impact of research.
- SocRSE Special Interest Group
 - Enable useful conversations.
 - Develop expertise and share knowledge
 - Ensure RSE role is recognized and supported
- Mailing list: GREENRESEARCHSOFTWARE@JISCMAIL.AC.UK

UNIVERSITY OF
CAMBRIDGE
Department of Public Health
and Primary Care

NIHR | Cambridge Biomedical
Research Centre

HDRUK
Health Data Research UK

UNDERSTANDING THE CARBON FOOTPRINT OF COMPUTING (AND WHY RSEs AND RESEARCHERS SHOULD THINK ABOUT IT)

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www.lannelongue.eu

HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPUTING HAS ENABLED AMAZING DISCOVERIES

NATIONAL GEOGRAPHIC LOGIN Renew SUBSCRIBE MENU

The Event Horizon Telescope—a planet-scale array of ground-based radio telescopes—has obtained the first image of a supermassive black hole and its shadow. The image reveals the central black hole of Messier 87, a massive galaxy in the Virgo cluster.
PHOTOGRAPH BY EVENT HORIZON TELESCOPE COLLABORATION

SCIENCE | STARSTRUCK

First-ever picture of a black hole unveiled

Event Horizon Telescope

Astronomers reveal first image of the black hole at the heart of our galaxy

May 12, 2022

DeepMind and EMBL release the most complete database of predicted 3D structures of human proteins

This article is also available in [Deutsch](#), [Français](#), [Italiano](#) and [Español](#).

Partners use AlphaFold, the AI system recognised last year as a solution to the protein structure prediction problem, to release more than 350,000 protein structure predictions including the entire human proteome to the scientific community.

Climate Change AI

Climate Change AI is a global initiative to catalyze impactful work at the intersection of climate change and machine learning.

and much more

HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPUTING HAS ENABLED AMAZING DISCOVERIES

...INCLUDING IN FIGHTING CLIMATE CHANGE

...BUT AT A COST: THE ICT SECTOR

ICT sector: 1.8%-2.8% of global
GHG emissions

(aviation sector, globally: 1.9%)

... BUT AT A COST: DATA CENTRES

Global GHG emissions of data centres

~126 Mt of CO₂e/year

Equivalent to American commercial aviation

Malmodin et al. 2024

*“ICT sector electricity consumption and
greenhouse gas emissions – 2020 outcome”*

<https://www.epa.gov/system/files/documents/2024-05/420f24022.pdf>

WHAT ABOUT THE SCIENCE WE DO? BIOLOGY

GWAS of 1,000 traits in UK Biobank
(225h / 100 GB per trait)

17.3 T CO₂e

Equivalent to...

...the carbon sequestered by 15 trees in 100 years

...346 flights between Paris and London

...but only 7.5 flights NYC-Melbourne

Metagenome assembly
of 100 soil samples
(1h / 130 GB)

14 kg CO₂e

...the carbon sequestered by a tree in 16 months

...30% of a flight between Paris and London

...0.6% of a flight NYC-Melbourne

WHAT ABOUT THE SCIENCE WE DO? BIOLOGY

GWAS of 1,000 traits in UK Biobank

(225h / 100 GB per trait)

17.3 T CO₂e

Metagenome assembly
of 100 soil samples

(1h / 130 GB)

14 kg CO₂e

RNA read alignments

10 million 100-bp to *P. falciparum*

(1h30 / 13 GB)

240 g CO₂e

WHAT ABOUT THE SCIENCE WE DO? AI

ESTIMATING THE CARBON FOOTPRINT OF BLOOM, A 176B PARAMETER LANGUAGE MODEL

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Hugging Face
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Model name	Number of parameters	Datacenter PUE	Carbon intensity of grid used	Power consumption	CO ₂ eq emissions	CO ₂ eq emissions × PUE
GPT-3	175B	1.1	429 gCO ₂ eq/kWh	1,287 MWh	502 tonnes	552 tonnes
Gopher	280B	1.08	330 gCO ₂ eq/kWh	1,066 MWh	352 tonnes	380 tonnes
OPT	175B	1.09 ²	231gCO ₂ eq/kWh	324 MWh	70 tonnes	76.3 tonnes ³
BLOOM	176B	1.2	57 gCO ₂ eq/kWh	433 MWh	25 tonnes	30 tonnes

UNFORTUNATELY...

Computing is **not** free

But from a **user** point of view, **it may look like it**

SO, WE HAVE A PROBLEM

Science generally aims at improving life on earth
Yet, it also contributes to worsening it through
climate change

Even if this contribution is small, shouldn't we at least think about it?

MORE FIELDS ARE NOW TACKLING THE ISSUE

Thinking Geographically about AI Sustainability

Meilin Shi¹, Kitty Currier², Zilong Liu¹, Krzysztof Janowicz^{1,2}, Nina Wiedemann³, Judith Versteegen⁴, Grant McKenzie⁵, Anita Graser⁶, Rui Zhu⁷, and Gengchen Mai⁸

ACL Anthology

Energy and Policy Considerations for Deep Learning in NLP

Emma Strubell, Ananya Ganesh, Andrew McCallum

arXiv.org > cs > arXiv:1910.09700

Computer Science > Computers and Society

[Submitted on 21 Oct 2019 (v1), last revised 4 Nov 2019 (this version, v2)]

Quantifying the Carbon Emissions of Machine Learning

Alexandre Lacoste, Alexandra Luccioni, Victor Schmidt, Thomas Dandres

From an environmental standpoint, there are a few crucial aspects of training a neural network that have a major impact on the quantity of carbon that it emits. These factors include: the location of the server used for training and the energy grid that it uses, the length of the training procedure, and even the make and model of hardware on which the training takes place. In order to approximate these emissions, we present our Machine Learning Emissions Calculator, a tool for our community to better understand the environmental impact of training ML models. We accompany this tool with an explanation of the factors cited above, as well as concrete actions that individual practitioners and organizations can take to mitigate their carbon footprint.

arXiv > cs > arXiv:2206.06370

Computer Science > Computers and Society

[Submitted on 12 Jun 2022]

Don't "research fast and break things": On the ethics of Computational Social Science

David Leslie

arXiv.org > cs > arXiv:1907.10597

Computer Science > Computers and Society

[Submitted on 22 Jul 2019 (v1), last revised 13 Aug 2019 (this version, v3)]

Green AI

Roy Schwartz, Jesse Dodge, Noah A. Smith, Oren Etzioni

The computations required for deep learning research have been doubling every four months, resulting in an estimated 300,000% increase from 2012 to 2019 [2]. These computations have a surprisingly large carbon footprint, which can make it difficult for academic institutions to justify the financial cost or "price tag" of such research. This position paper advocates for more inclusive and sustainable research practices, including reporting the carbon footprint of AI research, and we propose reporting the carbon footprint of AI research to make AI both greener and more inclusive.

arXiv > physics > arXiv:2203.12389

Physics > Physics and Society

[Submitted on 23 Mar 2022 (v1), last revised 23 Aug 2022 (this version, v2)]

Climate impacts of particle physics

Kenneth Bloom, Veronique Boisvert, Daniel Britzger, Micah Buuck, Astrid Eichhorn, Michael Headley, Kristin Lohwasser, Petra Merkel

ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

On the Dangers of Stochastic Parrots: Can Language Models Be Too Big?

Authors: Emily M. Bender, Timnit Gebru, Angelina McMillan-Major, Shmargaret Shmitchell

Publication: FAccT '21: Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency

nature astronomy

Explore content | Journal information | Publish with us

nature > nature astronomy > comment > article

Comment | Published: 10 September 2020

The ecological impact of high-performance computing in astrophysics

Simon Portegies Zwart

Nature Astronomy 4, 819–822 (2020) | Cite this article

1835 Accesses | 10 Citations | 500 Altmetric | Metrics

Computer use in astronomy continues to increase, and so also its impact on the environment. To minimize the effects, astronomers should avoid interpreted scripting languages such as Python, and favour the optimal use of energy-efficient workstations.

OHBM Sustainability & Environmental Action
Special Interest Group

Keep IT Green

KIG: a tool for Carbon footprint monitoring in physics research

Francesco Minarini, PhD student in Physics @University of Bologna, Italy and INFN

research area: Green Computing for High Energy Physics

International Symposium on Grids & Clouds (ISGC) 2023, Academia Sinica, Taipei, Taiwan. 03/24/2023

NEUROVIEW | VOLUME 106, ISSUE 1, P17-20, APRIL 08, 2020

How Can Neuroscientists Respond to the Climate Emergency?

Adam R. Aron • Richard B. Ivry • Kate J. Jeffery • ... Robert Schmidt • Christopher Summerfield • Anne E. Urai • Show all authors

Open Access • DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2020.02.019> • Check for updates

Concordat for the Environmental Sustainability of Research and Innovation Practice

The UK research and innovation (R&I) sector have co-developed a voluntary environmental sustainability concordat. The concordat represents a shared ambition for the UK to continue delivering cutting-edge research, but in a more environmentally responsible and sustainable way.

“By signing this concordat, we recognise the need to change how we conduct R&I as well as promote wider solutions. We agree to take shared action now and into the future to reduce and eliminate our own environmental impacts and emissions and achieve the transition to sustainable practices.”

Cancer Research UK Science and Innovation

10,255 followers

11h · 🌐

[+ Follow](#)

We've signed a concordat, co-developed with the UK Research & Innovation sector, agreeing on a common ambition for the UK to continue delivering cutting-edge research in a more environmentally res; ...see more

Jo Allatt MIEMA CEnv · 2nd

UKRI Head of Sustainability (Engagement and Policy)

5h · 🌐

[+ Follow](#) ...

I am pleased to say that UKRI have become a signatory to the new cross-sector concordat for the environmental sustainability of research practice published today. This is part of UKRI's commitment to progressive ...see more

Andrea Hodgetts · 2nd

Sustainable Research Manager | Partnership and Project ...

9h · 🌐

[+ Follow](#) ...

Today I'm all about celebrating the publication of the Concordat for the Environmental Sustainability of Research and Innovation Practice and UCL's commitment in this space as one its initial signatories! ...see more

Wellcome Trust

151,348 followers

10h · 🌐

[+ Follow](#)

We've joined 17 other UK organisations as initial signatories of the Concordat for the Environmental Sustainability of Research and Innovation Practice - and launched a new funding policy in the process. ...see more

COSTS AND BENEFITS

*Estimate and report
your own footprint
for your projects*

*...and include it in
your cost-benefit
analysis*

“Digital technologies developed and deployed in pursuit of net zero **must be energy-proportionate** – ie they must bring environmental or societal benefits that outweigh their own emissions.”

COSTS AND BENEFITS

*Estimate and report
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*...and include it in
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“Digital technologies developed and deployed in pursuit of net zero **must be energy-proportionate** – ie they must bring environmental or societal benefits that outweigh their own emissions.”

The solutions we develop **benefit the least populations who suffer the most from climate change**, it’s true for health research, AI and probably most fields of science.

UNDERSTANDING THESE IMPACTS

BREAKING DOWN THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF COMPUTING

Embodied
VS
use-stage

Carbon footprint
VS
broader environmental impacts

Computing
VS
storage

BREAKING DOWN THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF COMPUTING

Embodied
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VS
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*>82% of the 54m of tonnes of e-waste are handled
by 12-56m informal waste workers worldwide*

18m children work in industries involving waste processing

E-waste are predicted to raise by 40% by 2030

Children and digital dumpsites

E-waste exposure and
child health

Environmental Footprint impact categories

Life cycle impact assessment results against Planetary Boundaries

Links with Planetary boundaries

Sustainable Development Goals

Sala et al. 2020

“Environmental sustainability of European production and consumption assessed against planetary boundaries”

BREAKING DOWN THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF COMPUTING

Embodied
VS
use-stage

Carbon footprint
VS
broader environmental impacts

Computing
VS
storage

Energy bill of an average data centre:

- 50% servers
- 10% storage
- 40% overheads (cooling)

Storage
~10 kgCO₂e/TB/year

THE CARBON FOOTPRINT OF COMPUTATION

Carbon footprint = energy used x carbon intensity

gCO_2e

kWh

gCO_2e/kWh

THE CARBON FOOTPRINT OF COMPUTATION: CARBON INTENSITY

THE ROLE OF RSEs

MINIMISING CARBON INTENSITY THROUGH SMART SCHEDULING

Carbon intensity in the last 24 hours

↓ Get hourly historical, live, and forecast data with Electricity Maps API

312 g

162 g

48% reduction in GHG emission by running a job at 12pm on Wednesday instead of 5am on Thursday

Carbon intensity in the last 24 hours

↓ Get hourly historical, live, and forecast data with Electricity Maps API

60% in this case

MINIMISING CARBON INTENSITY THROUGH SMART SCHEDULING

CATS

Climate-Aware Task Scheduler

CATS is a Climate-Aware Task Scheduler. It schedules cluster jobs to minimize predicted carbon intensity of running the process. It was created as part of the [2023 Collaborations Workshop](#).

Currently CATS only works in the UK, if you are aware of APIs for realtime grid carbon intensity data in other countries please open an issue and let us know.

Software
Sustainability
Institute

IDENTIFY FURTHER OPPORTUNITIES FOR MORE SUSTAINABLE COMPUTING

Table 3
Results for binary-trees, fannkuch-redux, and fasta.

binary-trees	Energy (J)	Time (ms)	Ratio (J/ms)	Mb
(c) C	39.80	1125	0.035	131
(c) C++	41.23	1129	0.037	132
(c) Rust ↓ ₂	49.07	1263	0.039	180
(c) Fortran ↑ ₁	69.82	2112	0.033	133
(c) Ada ↓ ₁	95.02	2822	0.034	197
(c) Ocaml ↓ ₁ ↑ ₂	100.74	3525	0.029	148
(v) Java ↑ ₁ ↓ ₁₆	111.84	3306	0.034	1120
(v) Lisp ↓ ₃ ↓ ₃	149.55	10570	0.014	373
(v) Racket ↓ ₄ ↓ ₆	155.81	11261	0.014	467
(i) Hack ↑ ₂ ↓ ₉	156.71	4497	0.035	502
(v) C# ↓ ₁ ↓ ₁	189.74	10797	0.018	427
(v) F# ↓ ₃ ↓ ₁	207.13	15637	0.013	432
(c) Pascal ↓ ₃ ↑ ₅	214.64	16079	0.013	256
(c) Chapel ↑ ₅ ↑ ₄	237.29	7265	0.033	335
(v) Erlang ↑ ₅ ↑ ₁	266.14	7327	0.036	433
(c) Haskell ↑ ₂ ↓ ₂	270.15	11582	0.023	494
(i) Dart ↓ ₁ ↑ ₁	290.27	17197	0.017	475
(i) JavaScript ↓ ₂ ↓ ₄	312.14	21349	0.015	916
(i) TypeScript ↓ ₂ ↓ ₂	315.10	21686	0.015	915
(c) Go ↑ ₃ ↑ ₁₃	636.71	16292	0.039	228
(i) Jruby ↑ ₂ ↓ ₃	720.53	19276	0.037	1671
(i) Ruby ↑ ₅	855.12	26634	0.032	482
(i) PHP ↑ ₃	1,397.51	42316	0.033	786
(i) Python ↑ ₁₅	1,793.46	45003	0.040	275
(i) Lua ↓ ₁	2,452.04	209217	0.012	1961
(i) Perl ↑ ₁	3,542.20	96097	0.037	2148
(c) Swift		n.e.		

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Science of Computer Programming

www.elsevier.com/locate/scico

Ranking programming languages by energy efficiency

Rui Pereira ^{a,b,*}, Marco Couto ^{c,b}, Francisco Ribeiro ^{c,b}, Rui Rua ^{c,b},
Jácome Cunha ^{c,b}, João Paulo Fernandes ^d, João Saraiva ^{c,b}

^a C4 — Centro de Competências em Cloud Computing (C4-UBI), Universidade da Beira Interior, Rua Marquês d'Ávila e Bolama, 6201-001, Covilhã, Portugal

^b HASLab/INESC Tec, Portugal

^c Universidade do Minho, Portugal

^d Departamento de Engenharia Informática, Faculdade de Engenharia da Universidade do Porto & CISUC, Portugal

(but many softwares we use e.g. in Python actually use efficient languages under the hood)

THE GREEN ALGORITHMS PROJECT

And how it can help in this task

ESTIMATING CARBON FOOTPRINTS IN PRACTICE

nature reviews methods primers

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Comment | [Published: 16 February 2023](#)

Carbon footprint estimation for computational research

[Loïc Lanelongue](#) ✉ & [Michael Inouye](#)

[Nature Reviews Methods Primers](#) **3**, Article number: 9 (2023) | [Cite this article](#)

187 Accesses | 23 Altmetric | [Metrics](#)

Data analysis relies heavily on computation, and algorithms have grown more demanding in terms of hardware and energy. Monitoring their environmental impacts is and will continue to be an essential part of sustainable research. Here, we provide guidance on how to do so accurately and with limited overheads.

Michael Inouye

EXISTING TOOLS

carbontracker

pypi v1.1.6 python 3.8 | 3.9 | 3.10 build passing License MIT

About

carbontracker is a tool for tracking and predicting the energy consumption and carbon footprint of training deep learning models as described in [Anthony et al. \(2020\)](#).

experiment-impact-tracker

The experiment-impact-tracker is meant to be a simple drop-in method to track energy usage, carbon emissions, and compute utilization of your system. Currently, on Linux systems with Intel chips (that support the RAPL or powergadget interfaces) and NVIDIA GPUs, we record: power draw from CPU and GPU, hardware information, python package versions, estimated carbon emissions information, etc. In California we even support realtime carbon emission information by querying caiso.com!

Once all this information is logged, you can generate an online appendix which shows off this information like seen here:

https://breakend.github.io/RL-Energy-Leaderboard/reinforcement_learning_energy_leaderboard/pongnoframeskip-v4_experiments/ppo2_stable_baselines,_default_settings/0.html

What it is

A lightweight and easy-to-use Python pip package

Emissions tracked based on your power consumption & location-dependent carbon intensity

Cloud Carbon Footprint

Cloud Carbon Emissions Measurement and Analysis Tool

Understand how your cloud usage impacts our environment and what you can do about it

TRACARBON

CUMULATOR — a tool to quantify and report the carbon footprint of machine learning computations and communication in academia and healthcare

Trébaol, Tristan

2020

Green Algorithms

How green are your computations?

Details about your algorithm

To understand how each parameter impacts your carbon footprint, check out the formula below and the [methods article](#).

Runtime (HH:MM)

Type of cores

CPUS

Number of cores

Model

GPUS

Number of GPUs

Model

Memory available (in GB)

Select the platform used for the computations

Select location

Do you know the real usage factor of your CPU?

Yes No

Do you know the real usage factor of your GPU?

Yes No

Do you know the Power Usage Efficiency (PUE) of your local data centre?

 2.37 kg CO₂e
Carbon footprint

 9.37 kWh
Energy needed

 2.59 tree-months
Carbon sequestration

 13.56 km
in a passenger car

 5 %
of a flight Paris-London

Share your results with [this link!](#)

Computing cores VS Memory

How the location impacts your footprint

ADVANCED SCIENCE

Open Access

Research Article | [Open Access](#) | [CC](#) [BY](#)

Green Algorithms: Quantifying the Carbon Footprint of Computation

Loïc Lannelongue

First published: 02 May 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.202100707>

THE GREEN ALGORITHMS CALCULATOR

calculator.green-algorithms.org

Jason Grealey

Michael Inouye

GREEN ALGORITHMS 4 HPC

```
GreenAlgorithms4HPC]$ myCarbonFootprint.sh --STARTDAY 2020-01-01 --ENDDAY 2020-06-01
```

GREEN ALGORITHMS 4 HPC

```
GreenAlgorithms4HPC]$ myCarbonFootprint.sh --STARTDAY 2020-01-01 --ENDDAY 2020-06-01
```

<https://github.com/GreenAlgorithms/GreenAlgorithms4HPC>


```
#####  
#  
# Your carbon footprint on CSD3 #  
# (2021-01-01 / 2021-12-31) #  
#  
#####
```

```
-----  
| 222 kgCO2e |  
-----
```

...This is equivalent to:

- 20 tree-years
- driving 1,268 km
- 4.44 flights between Paris and London

...26.0% of your jobs failed, which represents a waste of 51 kgCO2e (55.26 tree-months).

...On average, you request at least 1.0 times the memory you need. By only requesting the memory you r

Energy used: 960.17 kWh

- CPUs: 88.91 kWh (9%)
- GPUs: 713.81 kWh (74%)
- Memory: 32.22 kWh (3%)
- Data centre overheads: 125.24 kWh (13%)

Carbon intensity used for the calculations: 231.12 gCO2e/kWh

Summary of your usage:

- First/last job recorded on that period: 2021-01-01/2021-12-08
- Number of jobs: 1,490 (1,102 completed)
- Core hours used/charged: 1,302.1 (CPU), 2,852.0 (GPU), 4,154.1 (total).
- Total usage time (i.e. when cores were performing computations):
 - CPU: 430 days 03:58:39
 - GPU: 118 days 20:01:30
- Total wallclock time: 132 days 10:49:44
- Total memory requested: 40,981 GB

*Let us know
if you try it!*

GREEN ALGORITHMS 4 HPC

```
GreenAlgorithms4HPC]$ myCarbonFootprint.sh --STARTDAY 2020-01-01 --ENDDAY 2020-06-01
```

<https://github.com/GreenAlgorithms/GreenAlgorithms4HPC>

Green Algorithms dashboard

University of ...

Last updated: Monday 08 Jan 2024, 22:24

Introduction
User's data (ll582)
Credits
Contact
FAQ

This is a prototype and the values are based on dummy logs for now!

Computing is a major contributor to energy consumption, and thus is one of the main sources of the carbon emission of our research. In the context of the global climate crisis, it is imperative that individuals and organizations find ways to assess then reduce the carbon footprint of their work.

This page aims to represent the carbon footprint that we are, collectively and individually, responsible for at University of SLURM jobs submitted to the CSD3 High Performance Cluster are logged automatically (including information such as resource requested, run time, memory efficiency, etc.), and the corresponding carbon footprint was calculated using the framework proposed by [Green Algorithms](#) and the following assumptions:

CPU	5.9 - 9.4 W/core (see here for models)
GPU	NVIDIA A100 (300 W) and NVIDIA Tesla P100 (250 W)
Memory power	0.3725 W/GB
Power usage effectiveness	1.15
Carbon intensity	231.12 gCO ₂ e/kWh
Energy cost	£0.34/kWh

We built this tool in the hope to raise awareness of computing usage, highlight resources waste, and foster good computing practices. This is intended to be a lightweight carbon footprint calculator, not a cluster monitoring system.

User's personal report: ll582

Find out your carbon footprint for the period.

 Carbon sequestration 0.572 tree-months			
--	--	--	---

COMING NEXT: GREEN ALGORITHMS DASHBOARD

Institutional dashboard to **monitor computing carbon footprint**
across research groups, units and departments

*Interested in piloting it
in your organisation?
Let's chat!*

*Already have
such a dashboard?
Let's chat!*

Matthias Blum

Alex Bateman

Michael Inouye

(EARLY RELEASE): NEXTFLOW PLUGIN

The screenshot shows the GitHub repository page for the 'nf-co2footprint' plugin. The page title is 'nf-co2footprint' and the description is 'A Nextflow plugin to estimate the CO₂ footprint of pipeline runs.' The main content area is titled 'Introduction' and contains the following text:

The nf-co2footprint plugin estimates the energy consumption for each pipeline task based on the Nextflow resource usage metrics and information about the power consumption of the underlying compute system. The carbon intensity of the energy production is then used to estimate the respective CO₂ emission.

The calculation is based on the carbon footprint computation method developed in the Green Algorithms project: www.green-algorithms.org

Green Algorithms: Quantifying the Carbon Footprint of Computation.
Lannelongue, L., Grealey, J., Inouye, M.,
Adv. Sci. 2021, 2100707. <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202100707>

The nf-co2footprint plugin generates a detailed TXT carbon footprint report containing the energy consumption, the estimated CO₂ emission and other relevant metrics for each task. Additionally, an HTML report is generated with information about the carbon footprint of the whole pipeline run and containing plots showing, for instance, an overview of the CO₂ emissions for the different processes.

Sabrina Krakau

Júlia Mir Pedrol

Phil Ewels

ESTIMATE ACKNOWLEDGE

Carbon impact and offsetting

We used GreenAlgorithms v.1.0 (ref. [121](#)) to estimate that the main computational work in this study had a carbon impact of at least 2,660 kg of CO₂ emissions (CO₂e), corresponding to 233 tree-years. As a commitment to the reduction of carbon emissions associated with computation in research, we consequently funded planting of 30 trees through a local Australian charity, which across their lifetime will sequester a combined estimated 8,040 kg of CO₂e, or three times the amount of CO₂e generated by this study.

Youwen Qin et al., Combined effects of host genetics and diet on human gut microbiota and incident disease in a single population cohort, Nature Genetics, 2022

Carbon impact and offsetting

We used GreenAlgorithms v.1.0 (ref. [84](#)) to estimate that the main computational work in this study had a carbon impact of at least 1,004 kg of CO₂ emissions (CO₂e), corresponding to 94 tree-years. As a commitment to the reduction of carbon emissions associated with computation in research, we consequently funded the planting of 45 trees through a local Australian charity, which across their lifetime will sequester a combined estimated 12,000 kg of CO₂e, or 12 times the amount of CO₂e generated by this study.

Yu Xu et al., An atlas of genetic scores to predict multi-omic traits, Nature, 2023

Carbon footprint of this project

We did our best to minimise greenhouse gas emissions related to this project and, using the Green Algorithms calculator (v2.1) [35], we estimated that the carbon footprint of this project was 51 kgCO₂e, which corresponds to 4.7 tree-years.

Lannelongue & Inouye, Pitfalls of machine learning models for protein-protein interaction networks, Bioinformatics, 2023

ESTIMATE ACKNOWLEDGE

Research | [Open Access](#) | [Published: 19 August 2022](#)

A comprehensive evaluation of microbial differential abundance analysis methods: current status and potential solutions

[Lu Yang](#) & [Jun Chen](#)

Microbiome **10**, Article number: 130 (2022) | [Cite this article](#)

others (146.1s vs 1.2–57.8 s). For large sample sizes, ZicoSeq can complete the analysis at an average of 5 and 25 min for $n = 1000$ and 5000 , respectively (Fig. S22). Based on the Green Algorithms (green-algorithms.org v2.1 [62]) and the geographic location of Minnesota, USA, ZicoSeq has a carbon footprint of 0.06 g CO_{2e}, 0.59 g CO_{2e}, and 3.16 g CO_{2e} for $n = 100$, 1000, and 5000, respectively.

Equivariant and Modular DeepSets with Applications in Cluster Cosmology

Leander Thiele*
Department of Physics
Princeton University
Princeton, NJ 08544

Miles Cranmer
Department of Astrophysical Sciences
Princeton University
Princeton, NJ 08544

William Coulton, Shirley Ho, David N. Spergel
Center for Computational Astrophysics

⁶Total compute cost is 13.4 (Tesla P100+9CPU) khr (1.09t CO_{2e} [26]) with a PyTorch [27] implementation.

tel-03726667, version 1

Theses

en The vehicle routing problem for flash floods relief operations

fr

Florent Dubois^{1,2} [Details](#)

- 1 IRIT-SEPIA - Système d'exploitation, systèmes répartis, de l'intergiciel à l'architecture
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- 2 UT3 - Université Toulouse III - Paul Sabatier

To conclude on the ethical aspect of my research, the carbon footprint of my thesis has been evaluated. It has been calculated using green-algorithms.org v2.0 [59]. The calculation considers the large-scale experimentation conducted on the platform Grid5000 located in France. Experimentation took a total of

576 hours of computations on 16 CPUs Xeon E5-2660 v3 and has drawn 207.47 kWh. It represents a carbon footprint of 8.08kg CO_{2e}.

GENOME
RESEARCH

HOME | ABOUT | ARCHIVE | SUBMIT | SUBSCRIBE | ADVERTISE | AUTHOR INFO | CONTACT

Efficient computation of Faith's phylogenetic diversity with applications in characterizing microbiomes

George Armstrong^{1,2,3}, Kalen Cantrell², Shi Huang^{1,2}, Daniel McDonald¹,

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0.5 GB of memory. Additionally, using Green Algorithms (Lannelongue et al. 2021), we estimated the carbon footprint of the scikit-bio reference implementation on the 20,000 sample table to be 12.84 g CO_{2e}, whereas we estimated the carbon footprint of SFPhD would be 0.04 g CO_{2e} in the United States, which is a 321-fold reduction in impact on global warming.

The logo for GreenDiSC is centered within a white circle. The word "Green" is in a green, sans-serif font, and "DiSC" is in a black, sans-serif font. To the right of "DiSC" is a circular icon consisting of two concentric circles, with the outer one being green and the inner one being black. Green circuit traces extend from the text and the icon.

GreenDiSC

Green DiSC is a new certification scheme which provides a roadmap for research groups and institutions who want to tackle the environmental impacts of their computing activities.

The vision

Evidence-based

3 levels of certification: Bronze, Silver, Gold

Free and open access

Community-based

Iterative

More info

info@greendisc.org

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the Software Sustainability Institute website. It includes the logo and menu items: About, News, blogs and events, Programmes, Training, and Resources. Below the navigation is a breadcrumb trail: Home | Green DiSC: a Digital Sustainability Certification. The main heading reads "Green DiSC: a Digital Sustainability Certification". A large image features the Green DiSC logo, which consists of a green circle with a white center containing the text "GreenDiSC" and a circuit-like pattern. The background of the image is a low-angle shot of green trees. Below the image, a short paragraph states: "Green DiSC is a new certification scheme which provides a roadmap for research groups and institutions who want to tackle the environmental impacts of their computing activities."

<https://www.software.ac.uk/GreenDiSC>

👁️👁️ WE ARE RECRUITING!

Range of roles

Research roles (research assistants/postdocs)

Software engineer

Project coordinator and community engagement

Adverts coming soon,
but get in touch already if interested!

LL582@medschl.cam.ac.uk
or just catch me at RSECon

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Clément Morand

LaBRI

Aurélie Bureau
Lucia Souza

How to follow the project and reach out

www.green-algorithms.org

 [@Loic_Lnlg](https://twitter.com/Loic_Lnlg)

LL582@medschl.cam.ac.uk

Becoming Greener in an RSE Group

Green RSE Community Building Session

Dr Laura Shemilt

Head of RSE

05/09/24

thinkbeforeprinting.org

Please consider the environment before printing

...this campaign is run by Ink Factory

Save trees, save paper

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/456500/daily-number-of-e-mails-worldwide/>

162596

0.5mm

Courtesy of Avery Pennington

Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

Living labs to improve the environmental sustainability of research infrastructure

1

UNDERSTAND

Integrate carbon footprint with the data lifecycle. Make environmental impact metrics available with experimental data to better understand the carbon footprint of science from instrument to open research publication.

2

REDUCE

Explore methods of reducing carbon emissions in the data lifecycle. Make data transfer and storage, software and compute architecture more environmentally sustainable.

3

EDUCATE

Engage with the scientific community to make them think about the climate impact of their data storage and processing. Educate them on how to reduce the cost of their research without compromising the science.

TRANSFER

Scratch
(filesystem)

Campaign
(object store)

Archive
(tape store)

STORAGE

Carbon Aware Keda Operator

<https://github.com/Azure/carbon-aware-keda-operator>

<https://grafana.com/grafana/dashboards/12239-nvidia-dcgm-exporter-dashboard/>

DisTraX

Creating an ephemeral
file system in
Distributed RAM

<https://github.com/rosalindfranklininstitute/DisTRaX>

FlowCron

A HPC workflow which
handles data transfer
and processing

Key Challenges to being a Green RSE:

Time

Green work will be deprioritised to achieve other key aims

Not a priority for some stakeholders

Level of engineering is hard, without the addition of sustainability

Key Opportunities to being a green RSE:

FUNDING AND
MANDATE

CARBON REDUCING
TECHNOLOGIES
EXIST

SECTOR/COMMUNITY
SUPPORT

AGILITY

ARCHER2 software energy use

Andy Turner, EPCC, University of Edinburgh, a.turner@epcc.ed.ac.uk

Data collection/analysis methodology

- Gathered energy use data for all job steps in Slurm in June 2022 (with non-zero energy use)
- Used Slurm job step Job Name property to match to software used
 - If srun is used to launch executables, Job Name corresponds to executable name
 - Use a library of regex to match to software packages
- <https://github.com/ARCHER2-HPC/usage-analysis/tree/main/app-data/code-definitions>
- Projects' supply a research area to match jobs to research areas
- Use Python Pandas and Seaborn to perform analysis and visualisation

Compute node: smallest unit of allocation on ARCHER2 – roughly corresponds to a standalone computer:

- 2x AMD EPYC™ 7742 64c, 2.25 GHz
- 256 GB DDR4
- 2x 100 Gbps Slingshot 10 interconnect interfaces
- Mean node power draw is the total energy use of the job step (in J) divided by the number of nodes and the job step residency (in s)
- Maximum theoretical power draw for an ARCHER2 compute node is around 700 W
- 986,983 job steps analysed - all job steps with energy data from Jul 2022 - before the reduction in default CPU frequency

Breakdown by software used on ARCHER2

Some interesting features:

- Met Office UM shows multiple distinct run types – possibly because it is a coupled application
- Consistently high power draw is typically from computational fluid dynamics software – surprising as these are often memory bound
- Many software clearly show features that indicate not all compute cores on a node are being used
- Need to repeat analysis in new setup with lower default frequency setting

Report covering methodology for data gathering and analysis

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7128628>